

EFFECT OF PRANAYAMA ON RATE PRESSURE PRODUCT IN PREHYPERTENSIVES

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ABSTRACT

Prehypertension, an intermediate stage between normal and hypertensive blood pressure, is linked to arterial stiffness, left ventricular hypertrophy, and elevated cardiovascular risks. Rate Pressure Product (RPP), a reliable marker of myocardial oxygen demand, is significantly influenced by lifestyle stressors and increased heart rate and blood pressure. This study examines the effect of Pranayama, a yogic breathing technique, on RPP in prehypertensives. Findings indicate that regular Pranayama practice enhances parasympathetic activity, reducing heart rate and systolic blood pressure, thereby decreasing RPP and myocardial oxygen demand. The results highlight Pranayama's potential as a non-pharmacological intervention for prehypertension management.

Keywords: Prehypertension, Rate Pressure Product (RPP), Pranayama, Myocardial Oxygen Demand, Cardiovascular Risk

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INTRODUCTION

Prehypertension is an intermediate stage between normal blood pressure and hypertension, which is associated with subclinical atherosclerosis and target organ damage (1). Prehypertension is defined as systolic blood pressure more than or equal to 120 - 139mmHg and or diastolic blood pressure more than or equal to 80 - 89mmHg (2). Prehypertension takes part in a dynamic process of stiffening and aging of the arteries (3).

According to the seventh report of the Joint National Committee (JNC) on prevention, detection, evaluation and treatment of blood pressure level, prehypertension requires attention and health promoting lifestyle modifications at an even earlier stage to prevent the progressive rise in blood pressure and cardiovascular disease. (4) Prehypertension can be considered as an emerging risk factor for adverse cardiovascular events(5).

Prehypertension has strong association with increased arterial stiffness, left ventricular hypertrophy and increased peripheral resistance even at a younger age group. Persistent prehypertension increases the progression of arterial stiffness (6). Damaged arteries not only leads to propagation of end organ damage but also leads to additional damage of the arteries and heart (3). In hypertensives, the myocardial oxygen demand (MVO_2) can be used as a better marker for predicting CVD. The rate pressure product (RPP) is a reliable index that best correlates with the myocardial oxygen demands of the heart. RPP is an indirect yet a reliable measure of the oxygen consumption of the heart in normal as well as individuals with ischemic heart disease (7).

Rate Pressure Product = HR X SBP (8,9)

The modern living lifestyle is known to produce various physical and psychological stresses resulting in elevated blood pressure (BP) and heart rate (HR). This can lead to increased myocardial oxygen demand (MVO_2). (7)

Numerous approaches are available for stress management that can decrease these patients suffering and enhance their quality of life. Yoga is an ancient system of relaxation, exercise and healing with origins in India. Pranayama, formal practice of controlling the breath, lies at the heart of yoga. Pranayama = prana + ayama, breathing has shown to alter autonomic activity as it increases parasympathetic activity (10).

AIM OF THE STUDY

To study the effect of pranayama on rate pressure product in prehypertensives.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design: Interventional study

Study Population: Prehypertensive patients were selected for the study. Prehypertension was considered as when systolic blood pressure is 120-139mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure 80-89mmHg. Sampling conducted among age group 35-50 years. After obtaining consent, heart rate, systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure were measured. The rate pressure product was calculated. One group were advised to follow lifestyle modification and other group were advised to practice pranayama along with lifestyle modification. The cases practiced Vibhagiya pranayama, Nadishuddi pranayama, Kapalabathi pranayama, Bhramhari pranayama, Sheetal pranayama and relaxed breathing for 30 mins under supervision. The heart rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure were recorded and rate pressure product in both the groups were calculated after three months. The same groups were followed for another 3 months and all the parameters were recorded after 6 months.

Inclusion criteria:

- Men and women of age group 35-50 years.
- Systolic blood pressure 120-139mmhg and/or diastolic blood pressure of 80-89mmhg.
- Willing to practice pranayama.

Exclusion criteria:

- Previous experience of yoga / pranayama.
- Chronic smokers
- Type 2 diabetes mellitus
- Kidney disease
- Chronic disorders like CAD, respiratory disorders like asthma.
- Age < 35years and >50 years.
- WHR \geq 0.90 cm in males & WHR \geq 0.85cm in females.

Sample size:

160 samples. 80 in each groups.

Statistical analysis:

The data were entered and analysed using SPSS software version 21.0. Variables were represented in mean \pm standard deviations. Paired t test was used as statistical test of significance and p value < 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Our study included, 160 subjects who were in the age group of 30 - 50 years of both sexes. They were grouped into cases and control, each consisting of 80. In case group, there were 42.5% males and 57.5% females. The mean baseline heart rate (HR) were 92.775 ± 1.172 . Only 1.3% subjects had heart rate in the range of 60 - 70 beats per minute. The mean baseline systolic blood pressure (SBP) were 129.775 ± 0.112 . About 98.8% subjects had their SBP in the range of 122 - 130mmHg. The mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) were 78.9 ± 0.341 . About 87.5% subjects had their DBP in the range of 72 - 80mmHg. The baseline rate pressure product (RPP) were 12047.8 ± 0.856 . About 38.8% and 37.5% subjects had their RPP in the range of 10,000 - 12,000 and 12,000 - 14,000 respectively. The mean heart rate (HR) after 3 months of pranayama were 83.35 ± 0.963 . The mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) after 3 months of pranayama were 119.425 ± 0.763 . The mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) after 3 months of pranayama were 75.1 ± 0.549 . The rate pressure product (RPP) after 3 months of pranayama were 9977.85 ± 0.779 . The mean heart rate (HR) after 6 months of pranayama were 79.9875 ± 0.821 . 12.5% subjects had heart rate in the range of 60 - 70 beats per minute. The mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) after 6 months of pranayama were 114.075 ± 0.615 . About 52.5% subjects had their SBP in the range of 92 - 110mmHg. The mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) after 6 months of pranayama were 70.625 ± 0.420 . About 22.5% subjects had their DBP in the range of 72 - 80mmHg. The rate pressure product (RPP) after 6 months of pranayama were 9099.95 ± 0.720 . About 22.5% and 56.3% subjects had their RPP in the range of 6000 - 8000 and 8000 - 10,000 respectively.

In control group, there were 57.5% males and 42.5% females. The mean baseline heart rate (HR) were 90.48 ± 0.922 . All controls had their systolic blood pressure of 130mmHg. The mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) were 78.8 ± 0.215 . The baseline rate pressure product (RPP) were $11,753.4 \pm 0.608$. The mean heart rate (HR) after 3 months of lifestyle modifications were 94.06 ± 0.746 . The mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) after 3 months of lifestyle modifications were 128.8 ± 0.711 . The mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) after 3 months of lifestyle modifications were 84.76 ± 0.616 . The rate pressure product (RPP) after 3 months of lifestyle modifications were $12,142.12 \pm 0.706$. The mean heart rate (HR) after 6 months of lifestyle modifications were 97.34 ± 0.905 . The mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) after 6 months of lifestyle modification were 131.72 ± 0.855 . The mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) after 6 months of lifestyle modifications were 87.08 ± 0.677 .

Effect of Pranayama on Rate Pressure Product in Prehypertensives

The rate pressure product(RPP) after 6 months of lifestyle modifications were 12894.46 ± 0.924 . About 36.3% and 40% subjects had their RPP in the range of 12,000 - 14,000 and 14,000 - 16,000 respectively. 1.3% subjects had their RPP above 16,000.

Rajni Goyal et al study concluded that pranayama leads to better control in mild hypertensive patients (1). Kalaivani et al noticed that there was better reduction in blood pressure when alternate nostril breathing was practiced along with antihypertensive medication (11).Veer Bhan et al study indicates that there is significant increase in vagal tone and reduction in sympathetic activity after pranayama training(12). Debra J Carlson et al study concluded that rate pressure product responses to isometric handgrip exercise indicate that it may be a safe alternative for people unable to perform recommended levels of aerobic exercise for blood pressure management (13). Shantanu Tiwari et al study concluded that, Bhramari pranayama and Anuloma-viloma pranayama may be used in the prevention of hypertension in prehypertensive phase(14). Ranjana Ganapat Tryambake et al study concluded that pranayama will assist in maintain normal blood pressure among hypertensive patient and help to reduce the complications of hypertension (15). Frederick L.Gobel et al concluded that heart rate and blood pressure are easily measured hemodynamic variables, are good indicators of myocardial oxygen consumption, during exercise in normotensive patients with ischemic heart disease(1).

Our study showed a significant reduction in heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure and rate pressure product among prehypertensive who practiced pranayama for 6 months. The above mentioned studies were in accordance with our study result. In our study the control groups who were asked to practice lifestyle modification showed no reduction in any parameters. Moreover, about 50% of the subjects progressed to hypertension.

Table 01: Rate pressure product baseline and after six months of pranayama among cases

Rate pressure product	Minimum value	Maximum value	Mean	Std. Deviation	Chi - square test value	P value
Before pranayama	8840	14560	12047.8	0.856	31.328	< 0.001
After pranayama	6820	12720	9099.95	0.720		

Figure 01: Rate pressure product baseline and after six months of pranayama among case

Table 02: Rate pressure product changes after six months of lifestyle modification among controls

RPP	Minimum value	Maximum value	Mean	Std. Deviation	Chi - square test value	P value
Before	9620	14690	11753.4	0.608	18.642	0.098
After	9460	15540	12894.96	0.043		

Figure 02: Rate pressure product changes after six months of lifestyle modification among controls

Parameters	Cases		Controls	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Heart rate				
Baseline	92.775	1.172	90.48	0.922
After 3 months	83.35	0.963	94.06	0.746
After 6 months	79.487	0.821	97.34	0.905
Systolic Blood Pressure				
Baseline	129.775	0.112	130	0
After 3 months	119.425	0.763	128.8	0.711
After 6 months	114.075	0.615	131.72	0.855
Diastolic Blood Pressure				
Baseline	78.9	0.341	78.8	0.265
After 3 months	75.1	0.549	84.76	0.616
After 6 months	70.625	0.420	87.08	0.677
Rate Pressure Product				
Baseline	12047.8	0.856	11753.4	0.608
After 3 months	9977.85	0.779	12142.12	0.706
After 6 months	9099.95	0.720	12894.46	0.924

CONCLUSION

The result of the present study indicates a reduction in rate pressure product in the prehypertensive who were practicing pranayama. The rate pressure product which is an indirect measure of myocardial oxygen consumption can be used as a non invasive index to evaluate the status of coronary perfusion and the competency of the myocardium in prehypertensive individuals. Our study shows that simple practice of pranayama can help in reducing the blood pressure and these simple practices can have favourable effect on the hemodynamic status of the individuals with pre-hypertension. These practices can be practiced by everyone and it does not need any special assistance. These practices does not have any adverse effect. Pranayama also has favourable effect on restoring and balancing the autonomic functions. There was no significant alteration in the heart rate among the control group. The control group also progressed to hypertension over a course. The main limitation of the study was sample size. The control groups were instructed to follow lifestyle modifications but no information or no supervision of the practices were done. The advantage of this study is by simple pranayama practices we can prevent a prehypertensive individuals progressing to hypertension. Hence, these practices can be effectively used as an adjunctive therapy along with routine conventional medications in-order to bring reduction in blood pressure among hypertensive individuals and can also be used along with lifestyle modification in prehypertensive individuals in preventing the individuals from progressing to hypertension.

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